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Effect Of Orientation On Role Of Financial Institutions On Poverty Reduction Among Small And Medium Enterprises In Taraba State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This research investigated the impact of orientation on the function of financial institutions in alleviating poverty among small and medium-sized firms in Taraba State. The study used a survey research approach and collected data from primary sources. Furthermore, the data were aggregated from the 726 questionnaires given, with 184 picked from small and micro-entrepreneurs using Cochran's simple random sampling approach. Additionally, the Foster-Greer-Thorbecke (FGT) and Sen-Shorrocks-Thon (SST) indices were used to assess poverty. The Gini Coefficient Index was developed to quantify income inequality. The FGT poverty rate, depth, and severity are 61.95%, 24.67%, and 12.92%, respectively, while the SST poverty rate is 32.68% and the Gini coefficient is 35.63%, showing a significant degree of poverty and income inequality among small and medium enterprises (SMEs). The volume of micro-credit from deposit money banks reduces income inequality by 0.009% for micro entrepreneurs and 0.012% for small-scale enterprises. The heteroskedasticity-robust standard analysis was conducted, revealing statistical significance at $p < 0.05$. The research determined that poverty and economic disparity are prevalent among micro and small-scale enterprises. This research advocates for an augmentation of microcredit volume and enhanced access to microcredit loans via policies and programs aimed at lowering interest rates and alleviating severe collateral requirements to foster sustainable economic growth in Taraba State.

Keywords: Financial Institutions, Poverty, micro and small scale entrepreneur, Gini index

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Since 70% of Nigerians reside in rural areas, many small and medium-sized businesses in these regions face even more severe poverty due to a lack of access to banking services. This highlights the critical role that financial institutions play in driving economic development in developing economies like Nigeria's. Only about one-third of Nigeria's economically engaged population has access to the country's official financial system; the other two-thirds do not. Microfinance organisations run by non-governmental organisations (NGOs), moneylenders, friends, family, and credit unions often assist this 65% of the population (Central Bank of Nigeria, 2011).

According to Jammeh (2000), microfinance and micro-credit offer a viable solution for expanding income and reducing poverty because formal financial systems fail to meet the needs of micro and small-scale companies, especially in rural areas. The poor are heavily involved in this informal sector. In order to alleviate poverty, increase self-employment, and generate income, microfinance and microcredit have gained recognition as a tool for transferring and supporting resources to low-income individuals. Therefore, improving the economic well-being of those in need, especially in rural regions, is critically dependent on the availability of sufficient credit. An important part of development strategy for the last few decades has therefore been making inexpensive financial services available to the poor.

The Central Bank of Nigeria defines small-scale companies (SMEs) as businesses with a yearly revenue of N25,000 to N500,000 (CBN, 2004). This is defined. SMEs are defined as businesses with five or more workers and a capital expenditure of five thousand Nigerian naira or less (Ogundele, 2007). Awoyemi, Akomolafe, & Osunyikanmi (2020) found that MSMEs differ from one nation to another; for example, a small business in the US does not always mean a small business in Nigeria. Companies are considered micro, small, and medium-sized if they have fewer than 300 workers and \$15 million in assets, or if they have less than 100 workers and \$3 million in sales, according to inter-American development (Dahlberg 2011). The Nigerian government's Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises Development Agency (SMEDAN) uses the following criteria to categorise MSMEs: the number of workers, the value of assets (not including land and buildings), and location. A micro-enterprise, often called a micro-business, is a very little company that employs only a handful of people. Businesses are classified as micro- or small-enterprises based on their size and the amount of capital they typically receive from banks or other financial organisations. On the other hand, small-enterprises are defined as businesses with ten or more employees and total assets (excluding land and building cost) between five and fifty million Naira. A large majority of micro-businesses focus on serving the immediate community. Micro-enterprises are tiny firms that rely on micro-credit, a kind of unsecured lending that is extended to individuals without a substantial credit history or stable job (Kenton, 2019). Whether it's the manufacture of garments and footwear or agricultural services, these firms play an essential role in improving the living conditions of people in developing nations. The local economy benefits and the owners' quality of life is enhanced by micro-enterprises. They increase buying power, raise incomes, and also provide new employment opportunities. Those in favour of micro-enterprises and micro-credit argue that these platforms help the poor by giving them access to stable incomes and jobs. According to Kenton (2019).

2.0 Literature Review

Most people living in poverty across the world are under the age of 18, have low levels of education, and work as micro or small-scale entrepreneurs. Many of these people also reside in rural regions. Combating severe poverty is an ongoing and difficult task. There has been a halt or even reversal in the fight against poverty in many countries because investment has been too muted and growth rates have been too sluggish to raise median incomes. Countries that have managed to escape fragile or conflict-affected situations (FCS) have reduced their poverty rate by more than half, whereas the 43 nations with the highest poverty rates are located in sub-Saharan African economies that are facing chronic fragility and conflict. Poverty rates in these countries have remained stagnant at 40% over the past decade. It is quite probable that this trend will reverse in 2020 as a result of global shocks like the COVID-19 issue and the oil price decline.

The poor would bear the brunt of the COVID-19 problem in terms of lost jobs, remittances, pricing, and services like healthcare and education. As the world economy enters a recession and GDP per capita drops dramatically, we will see an increase in poverty rates for the first time since 1998. Everything that has been accomplished in the last five years will be completely wiped out by the ongoing catastrophe. Depending on the assumptions used about the extent of the economic shock, the World Bank predicts that between 40 million and 60 billion people would descend into severe poverty (living on less than \$1.90 per

day) in 2020 as a consequence of COVID-19, compared to 2019. By 2020, the world's severe poverty rate could have increased by an additional 0.3 to 0.7 percent points, reaching around 9% (World Bank, 2020). In its most recent poverty and inequality report, the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) defined natural poverty as an annual expenditure below N137, 430 (N376.50 per day or roughly \$1 on N360/\$). With a population of over 200 million, this means that 82.9 million Nigerians live in poverty, and the number is expected to rise steadily over the next few decades. NBS recorded a poverty rate of 62.6% in 2010 using a per capita method; moreover, 11 million people were lifted out of poverty in Nigeria within a decade (NBS 2020). Using the per-capita method, NBS recorded a poverty rate of 62.6% in 2010, hence this is lower. Compared to urban regions, where the poverty headcount was 18% in 2019, rural areas had a greater headcount of 52.1%. In terms of poverty rates, the states with the highest were Sokoto (87.73%), Taraba (87.72%), and Jigawa(87.02%), while the lowest were Lagos(4.5%), delta(6%), and Osun (8.5%). In addition, the World Bank-coordinated research estimated a 12.9% poverty gap, or depth of poverty, which translates to an average of almost N18, 000.00 less per capita consumption than what is needed to be considered poor.

Table 1: Poverty and Inequality Indices by States

State	Poverty head count rate	Poverty gap index	Squared poverty gap index (Severity)
NIGERIA	40.09	12.85	5.63
Urban	18.04	4.47	1.68
Rural	52.10	17.42	7.78
Abia	30.67	7.15	2.59
Adamawa	75.41	27.64	13.21
Akwalbom	26.82	7.25	2.74
Anambra	14.78	3.24	1.06
Bauchi	61.53	20.50	9.07
Bayelsa	22.61	5.25	1.89
Benue	32.90	8.43	3.05
Borno			
CrossRiver	36.29	9.66	3.60
Delta	6.02	0.94	0.21
Ebonyi	79.76	34.09	17.05
Edo	11.99	2.90	1.01
Ekiti	28.04	6.16	2.00
Enugu	58.13	16.00	6.34
Gombe	62.31	20.03	8.97
Imo	28.86	6.89	2.35
Jigawa	87.02	38.73	20.53
Kaduna	43.48	15.51	6.74
Kano	55.08	15.24	5.68
Katsina	56.42	16.18	6.50

Kebbi	50.17	15.14	6.19
Kogi	28.51	6.19	2.01
Kwara	20.35	4.45	1.50
Lagos	4.50	0.67	0.18
Nasarawa	57.30	16.87	6.62
Niger	66.11	21.68	9.12
Ogun	9.32	1.63	0.44
Ondo	12.52	2.28	0.58
Osun	8.52	1.43	0.44
Oyo	9.83	1.85	0.52
Plateau	55.05	17.80	7.61
Rivers	23.91	5.46	1.73
Sokoto	87.73	38.82	20.34
Taraba	87.72	42.38	24.44
Yobe	72.34	26.48	12.84
Zamfara	73.98	24.95	10.41
FCT	38.66	9.77	3.80

Source: Nigeria Living Standards Survey, NBS 2018-19.

Note:* The estimates exclude Borno State.

Table 2. Poverty Headcount Rate by Household Head's Education Level and Sex

State	Non-education/less than primary education		Primary Education		Secondary Education		Post-secondary education	
	Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female
NIGERIA	66.17	34.72	41.25	26.93	25.00	14.08	18.13	5.66
Urban	43.14	24.66	19.16	19.35	12.97	11.20	8.86	3.42
Rural	70.82	39.17	50.33	32.74	35.87	18.96	31.20	10.15

Table 3. Poverty Headcount Rate by Household Head's Income-generating Activity and Sex

State	Agriculture Only		Non-farm Enterprise Only		Wage Work Only		Diversified		Apprenticeship/Networking	
	Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female
NIGERIA	58.76	37.75	25.45	19.45	17.53	13.99	46.90	31.54	34.24	24.13
Urban	30.11	27.96	15.22	18.12	11.87	11.38	23.92	24.99	18.60	11.00
Rural	63.20	39.02	41.68	22.48	28.72	21.14	53.25	33.79	47.14	34.81

Table 4. Poverty Headcount Rate by Household Size

State	1 person	2-4 people	5-9 people	10-19 people	20 or more people
NIGERIA	2.66	17.88	40.90	67.27	77.66
Urban	1.66	5.23	19.07	44.47	71.57
Rural	3.61	27.52	53.18	73.79	79.60

Top category (20 or more people) is too small-just 17 observations for urban areas

Source: NBS 2019

2.1.1 Neo-Classical Theory of Poverty

Neo-classical thinkers linked poverty to a lack of public and private resources, as well as market failures that prevent low-income people from getting loans and make some bad decisions seem reasonable, as well as obstacles to learning due to factors like age, immigration status, bad health, and lack of job opportunities for families with only one breadwinner. "The publishing by Alfred Marshal of his 'principles of economics' in 1890 is considered to be one of the primary advances forward before the emergence of Neoclassical economics," (Davis and Sanchez-Martinez, 2014) state. Market failures such as externalities, moral hazard, adverse selection, incomplete information, uncertainty, and scepticism, as well as unequal initial endowments of talents, skills, and capital, are blamed for exacerbating poverty, according to Davis (2007). They proposed the following theories and factors as potential pathways into poverty: the monetary approach; incentives; failure of market as well as accessibility to credit markets; human capital theory; health; demography; and migration and ethnic minorities.

2.1.2 Credit to Small and Medium Scale Enterprises by Deposit Money Bank in Nigeria

Like their counterparts in other countries, small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs) in Nigeria have had trouble gaining access to the loans they need to grow. Since the Nigerian stock market has not grown into a reliable source of capital for businesses, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in the country have had to rely on loans from Nigerian banks or other non-bank sources to keep their operations afloat. To make matters worse, the liberalisation of Nigeria's financial system during the structural adjustment program (1986–1993) allowed interest and exchange rates to rise as the country's economy shifted towards a market orientation and the government gave up control of these and other monetary mechanism indicators, further limiting the access of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) to credit. There have been more problems with the financial system, and as always, some people will come out on top and others will fall by the wayside. In the context of Nigeria's business sector, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) took a particularly hard blow as banks tightened their lending regulations, cutting off even more access for SMEs.

A recent example of such a problem is the worldwide financial crisis of 2007 (Oluwarotimi, & Adamu, 2017). Small and medium-sized enterprise (SME) credit in Nigeria peaked in 1992 at 27% of total bank credit, as seen in the following graph. Still, Nigerian deposit money banks have been steadily cutting down on lending to small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) throughout the years, with the percentage dropping to 0.1% in 2010 and staying there until 2014. From 1992 to 2015, SME credit in Nigeria was generally trending downwards by deposit money banks. The only exceptions to this downward trend were the years 1994–1996 and 2001–2002, which show small but noticeable increases in SME bank credit.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

A questionnaire with a self-structured design is sent to the main source in order to gather data from them. To be more specific, questionnaires will be sent to a selection of micro and small-scale businesses located inside Jalingo, which is the capital of Taraba state in Nigeria. The Central Bank of Nigeria, the Deposit

Money Bank, the Bank of Agriculture, the National Bureau of Statistics, the Bank of Industry, the Small and Medium-Sized Enterprise Development Agency of Nigeria, the Cooperative Society, Money Lender Journals and Text books, the internet, and other sources will be consulted in order to acquire secondary data. In addition, we will be contacting a few officials from the microfinance institution that is part of the local government as well as leaders from the villages that have been chosen.

4.0 DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

Socioeconomic and Demographic Characteristics of the respondents

Gender and Age Distribution of the Respondent

The gender breakdown of the respondents is as follows: 56.7% men and 43.3% female, according to table 4.1. Males make up a bigger proportion of the responders generally. Table 4.1 further reveals that 16.4% of those who responded are between the ages of 22 and 31, 39.3% are between the ages of 32 and 41, 27.2% are between the ages of 42 and 51, 9.4% are between the ages of 52 and 61, and 7.7% are above the age of 61. The majority of responders are male and fall within the age category of 32–41 years, according to the statistics.

Micro and small-scale entrepreneurs in the study area are mostly male (56.7% of respondents), suggesting that they are more likely to be involved in this type of business than their female counterparts. The majority of these entrepreneurs are between the ages of 32 and 41, which is a young, active population with the ability to work and earn a living but limited financial resources. By providing them with financial support, we can help these entrepreneurs reach their full potential and alleviate poverty and income inequality.

Table 4: Gender and age groups of the respondent

<i>Gender of Respondent</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
Male	517	56.7
Female	395	43.3
Total	912	100
<i>Age Group</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
22-31	150	16.4
32-41	358	39.3
42-51	248	27.2
52-61	86	9.4
Above 61	70	7.7
Total	912	100

Source: Authors computation (2025)

According to Table 4.2, three-quarters of the respondents have never attended school, and almost a third have only completed elementary school. At 22.4%, the next highest level of education reported was secondary school, and at 9.3%, the highest level of education reported was post-secondary. On top of that, most of the people who filled out the survey never attended college.

According to the data below, most of the participants have only completed secondary school or are illiterate. This could be a contributing factor to the high rates of poverty and income inequality among the micro and small-scale entrepreneurs in the area. It also suggests that most of these entrepreneurs don't know how to take advantage of the financial assistance offered by micro-credit institutions in the area to grow their businesses.

Table 5: The distribution of the level of education respondents

Level of Education	Frequency	Per cent
No education	341	37.4
Primary	282	30.9
Secondary	204	22.4
Post-Secondary	85	9.3
Total	912	100

Source: Authors computation (2025)

The distribution of Marital Status and tribe respondents

As can be seen in Table 5, 23.8% of the people surveyed have said that they have never been married, 48.9% of married individuals are monogamous, 11.6% of married polygamous, 8.3% of divorced or separated individuals are in an informal union, and 3% of widowed individuals are in an informal union. It can be seen from the findings that a greater proportion of the individuals who participated in the survey are monogamous and married. According to the data shown in table 4.3, 48.2% of the respondents are of the Hausa ethnicity, 17.8% of the respondents are of the Yoruba ethnicity, 25.1% of the respondents are of the Igbo ethnicity, and 8.9% of the respondents belong to other tribes.

In summary, the vast majority of respondents are members of the Hausa tribe. This might be due to the fact that the Hausa language is the most generally spoken language in the region under investigation, and it is also the language that is most often used for communication due to the high level of illiteracy that exists in the country. Additionally, the majority of respondents in the survey had a monogamous marital status. The findings of this survey are consistent with the prior discovery that the majority of the respondents in the study region adhere to the Christian faith.

Table 6: Marital Status and Tribe of the respondents

<i>Marital Status</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
Never married	217	23.8
Married monogamous	446	48.9
Married polygamous	106	11.6
Divorced/separated	76	8.3
Informal union	40	4.4
Widowed	27	3.0
Total	912	100
<i>Tribe</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
Hausa	440	48.2
Yoruba	162	17.8
Igbo	229	25.1
Others	81	8.9
Total	912	100.0

Source: Authors computation (2024)

Relationship among Gender, Age Group, Marital Status and Level of Education

Table 4 displays the correlation between the study's respondents' educational attainment, gender, age group, marital status, and kind of employment. According to the correlation, out of the total number of male respondents, 193 have never attended school, 135 have completed elementary school, 137 have completed high school, and 52 have completed college. Among the women who filled out the survey, 148 have never attended school, 147 have completed elementary school, 67 have completed secondary school,

and 33 have completed post-secondary education. As a whole, the responders lack formal schooling. As an added bonus, table 4.4 displays the correlation between respondents' ages and degrees of education. In the age group of 22–31, 61 respondents have no formal education, 42 have completed elementary school, 28 have completed secondary school, and 19 have completed post-secondary education, according to the correlation.

Among those who responded between the ages of 32 and 41, 128 have never attended school, 94 have completed elementary school, 103 have completed secondary school, and 33 have completed some kind of post-secondary education. In addition, among those aged 42–51, 107 have never attended school, 85 have completed elementary school, 36 have completed high school, and 20 have completed college. In addition, 25 people in the 52-61 age group have never attended school, 34 have completed elementary school, 19 have completed high school, and 8 have completed college. Finally, among those aged 61 and above, 20 have never attended school, 27 have completed elementary school, 18 have completed high school, and 5 have completed college. In general, those between the ages of 22 and 31, 32 and 41, and 42 and 51 have the lowest rates of formal education, whilst those between the ages of 51 and 61 and those above 61 have the highest rates of elementary education.

Source of Credit

Table 4.9 illustrates the sources of credit used by the respondents. The findings indicate that 8.7% of respondents acquire microcredit from deposit money banks (DMB), 4.6% from the Bank of Industry (BOI), 0% from microfinance banks (MFB) due to the absence of such institutions in the state, 8.6% from agricultural banks, 8.9% from cooperatives, and 68.6% from money lenders, attributed to a low level of awareness regarding the functions of financial institutions in the state, while 0.7% of respondents obtain microcredit from relatives.

The majority of respondents acquire microcredit from moneylenders owing to a lack of information about the function of financial institutions and the respondents' low educational levels in the State.

Table 8: Source of Credit

<i>Source of Credit</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
Deposit Money Bank	79	8.7
Bank of Industry	42	4.6
Microfinance banks	Nil	Nil
Agriculture Bank	78	8.6
Cooperative Bank	81	8.9
Money lenders	626	68.6
Relations	6	0.7
Total	912	100

Source: Authors computation (2024)

5.0 SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The research was conducted using 726 questionnaires completed by individuals from Taraba. The FGT and SST indices were used to assess the poverty levels among micro and small enterprises. The findings indicate that the amount of microcredit influences poverty levels; specifically, microcredit obtained via deposit money banks and microfinance institutions alleviates poverty, but microcredit acquired through personal relationships exacerbates poverty.

The research revealed that deposit money banks, microfinance banks, cooperative banks, land collateral, house collateral, and years of operation positively and significantly enhance access to microcredit on a weekly, monthly, and quarterly basis, whereas interest rates, moneylenders, and the scale of microbusinesses increase access to microcredit annually and biennially. The survey also indicated that impoverishment is more pronounced among females than males based on the low-income rate. Poverty

depth is greater among females than males, although poverty severity is more pronounced among males than females.

Recommendations

The government must enhance efforts to educate individuals about the true purpose of savings. A reorientation for these firm owners is necessary prior to any government action; otherwise, the revenues from such intervention may be misappropriated.

The loan amount should be augmented to satisfy borrower needs, but this must be executed with caution, taking into account the client's repayment capacity and the appropriateness of each project. This is essential for company growth, since micro business owners need microcredit to develop their enterprises, therefore generating employment and contributing to the achievement of Sustainable Development Goal one, which focusses on poverty alleviation.

The Nigerian Government must foster an enabling environment for the effective operation of microfinance institutions, which should implement more comprehensive micro credit schemes and institutional policy frameworks to facilitate access to funds for impoverished micro and small-scale entrepreneurs lacking adequate collateral, particularly in agro-allied industries and other business ventures.

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